

On Λ -Fractional Maxwell Equations

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Abstract: Adapting the Λ -fractional derivative, in fact the unique fractional derivative corresponding to a differential and able to generate fractional differential geometry, fractional Maxwell's equations are defined for Electric and Magnetic fields. That fractional theory concerning Maxwell's equations may be used in complex systems exhibiting memory effects. Further, those equations concern micro or nano-scale where the various principles demand non-local derivatives.

Key words: fractional Λ -derivative, differential, fractional Λ -space, initial space, Maxwell's electromagnetic equations, magnetic induction, dielectric displacement.

1. Introduction

The nonlocal continuum field theories of material bodies are important in micro and nano regions, where non-local intermolecular attractions are applied. Stress fields in the dislocation regions, singularities at the point of force application, generally fracture of solids, viscosity in fluids, flowing in microscopic tubes, are some of the problems demanding non-local analysis.

Fractional analysis, concerning fractional derivatives and integrals, is a non-local analysis originated in 1695 by Leibnitz, trying to establish the non-local derivative, since he already had established the local one. Many eminent mathematicians, like Liouville, Laplace, Euler, Poincare, Riemann were involved in establishing fractional derivatives and integrals. Although many versions of fractional derivatives have been presented, all those fractional derivatives are not real mathematical derivatives, fulfilling the demands of differential topology, just to correspond to differentials. Therefore, those derivatives are rather differential operators than derivatives. However, the known fractional derivatives like Riemann-Liouville, Caputo, etc are questionable in formulating fractional differential equations, since differential equations are mainly derived from principles expressing zero differentials. Yet, there was an increased use of the fractional analysis in the last thirty years, due to the need for expressing non-local interaction. Besides, many physical problems have been discussed, involving fractional analysis in fractal geometrical shapes. Fractional calculus has been an indispensable tool in various branches in mechanics, physics, engineering, control theory, and economics [5–8]. Classical references are the books [9–12] including also various applications. Especially, Fractional derivatives have been used in discussing viscoelasticity [13], diffusion problems [14], flow in anomalous porous media [15]. Fractional generalizations of Hamiltonian and gradient systems [16] are also important. Fractional control problems have also been presented [21–25] with important real applications.

Nevertheless, all the problems expressed with fractional derivatives (operators) have problems in their

mathematical establishment, since the so called fractional derivatives cannot correspond to a differential, according to differential topology. Differential Topology demands three basic properties from a derivative, just to correspond to a differential generating geometry. Those properties are, linearity, the conventional law of the derivative of the product (Leibniz's law) and the law of the differentiation of the composite functions (chain rule). Although, the well known fractional derivatives fulfill the linearity law, fail to satisfy the other two conditions. Hence fractional differential geometry and fractional differential equations lack of the mathematical accuracy that physics, biology, economy, mechanics etc demand. Trying to find a way out Lazopoulos [17], presented the Λ -fractional derivative satisfying all the requirements differential topology dictates for the existence of a fractional derivative. In fact a space dual to the initial, the Λ -fractional space is defined where the Λ -fractional derivative becomes local in the Λ -fractional space. Hence differential geometry and differential equations may be solved and may mathematically be established in that space. Then, the various results may be transferred into the initial space. Let us point out that derivatives do not exist in the initial space. The proposed derivative has been used in solving non-local problems in mechanics, Lazopoulos [18].

Taking into consideration lattice dynamics, the behavior and the nature of the dielectric is explained into the context of non-local linear electromagnetic theory. Various waves, like optical and Alfvén waves, gyroscopic media, polaritons and currents are explained. Memory dependent electromagnetic elastic solids and electromagnetic thermofluids may be discussed in non-local theory. Baleanu et al.[19] and Ortigueira et al [20] have stressed the importance of the fractional Maxwell's equations. In the present work, the fractional Maxwell's electromagnetic equations will be formulated into the context of Λ -fractional theory. Following that theory, the fractional derivatives and the differential geometry are valid in the Λ -fractional space. Performing the analysis in the Λ -space, in the conventional way, the results may be transferred into the initial space. The theory is explained with an application. In the following chapters the Λ -fractional derivative will be discussed with some mathematical applications. Although that chapter might have been omitted, since the reader could find it elsewhere, the absence of that chapter would have almost done the present work inaccessible.

2. The Λ -Fractional Derivative

For an introduction to Fractional Analysis, the interested reader should be informed by refs.[9–12]. Nevertheless, a brief outline is presented in this chapter just to make the present work more accessible. As far as the left and right fractional integrals are concerned, they are defined by,

$${}_a I_x^\gamma f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \int_a^x \frac{f(s)}{(x-s)^{1-\gamma}} ds, \quad (1)$$

$${}_x I_b^\gamma f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \int_x^b \frac{f(s)}{(s-x)^{1-\gamma}} ds, \quad (2)$$

with γ been the order of fractional integrals and $\Gamma(x) = (x-1)!$ with $\Gamma(\gamma)$ Euler's Gamma function. Further the Riemann-Liouville (RL) fractional derivatives are defined by:

$${}^R L D_x^\gamma f(x) = \left(\frac{d}{dx}\right)^{m+1} ({}_a I_x^{m-\gamma} f(x)) \quad (3)$$

and

$${}_x R L D_b^\gamma f(x) = \left(-\frac{d}{dx}\right)^{m+1} ({}_x I_b^{m-\gamma} f(x)) \quad (4)$$

where, Eq.(2.3) defines the left and Eq.(2.4) the right fractional derivatives. In addition, the Riemann-Liouville fractional derivatives with the corresponding fractional integrals are related by:

$${}_{\alpha}^{RL}D_x^{\gamma}({}_{\alpha}I_x^{\gamma}f(x)) = f(x) \quad (5)$$

Nevertheless, the so called fractional derivatives do not have the properties required by differential topology, just to generate fractional differential. In fact although the linearity property is valid, the laws of fractional derivatives for the product (Leibnitz rule) and the composite functions are not valid. Therefore no differential geometry exists and also the various fractional differential equations might not be well posed. Lazopoulos [17] introduced the Λ -fractional derivative, that satisfies the requirements of differential topology, for corresponding to a differential. Hence fractional differential geometry may be generated and fractional differential equations may be well posed. Proceeding to the definition of Λ -fractional derivative,

$${}_{\alpha}^{\Lambda}D_x^{\gamma}f(x) = \frac{{}_{\alpha}^{RL}D_x^{\gamma}f(x)}{{}_{\alpha}^{RL}D_x^{\gamma}x} \quad (6)$$

It is evident that for $0 < \gamma < 1$,

$${}_{\alpha}^{\Lambda}D_x^{\gamma}f(x) = \frac{\frac{d_{{}_{\alpha}I_x^{1-\gamma}}f(x)}{dx}}{\frac{d_{{}_{\alpha}I_x^{1-\gamma}}x}{dx}} = \frac{d_{{}_{\alpha}I_x^{1-\gamma}}f(x)}{d_{{}_{\alpha}I_x^{1-\gamma}}x} \quad (7)$$

In addition,

$$X = {}_{\alpha}I_x^{1-\gamma}x \quad \text{and} \quad F(X) = {}_{\alpha}I_x^{1-\gamma}f(x). \quad (8)$$

Hence, the Λ -FD gets the formulation of a conventional local derivative in the dual fractional Λ - space $(X, F(X))$. Since, equation (8) yields

$$X = \frac{x^{2-\gamma}}{\Gamma(3-\gamma)} \quad (9)$$

and equations (8),(9) give:

$$F(x) = {}_{\alpha}I_x^{1-\gamma}f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\gamma)} \int_{\alpha}^x \frac{f(s)}{(x-s)^{\gamma}} ds, \quad (10)$$

The dual Λ -space may be defined by the X and $F(X)$ coordinates. In that space (dual to the initial) space the Λ -derivative behaves as a local one. Inverting equation (9) it appears,

$$x = (\Gamma(3-\gamma)X)^{\frac{1}{2-\gamma}} = x(X) \quad (11)$$

Proceeding further to the definition of the fractional Λ -space, inserting $x(X)$ into equation (10), the function $F(x)$ may be expressed as a function of

$$F(X) = F(x(X)) \quad (12)$$

Performing the analysis in the dual Λ -fractional space, following the conventional way, the results may be transferred to the initial space recalling equation (5),

$${}_{\alpha}^{RL}D_x^{1-\gamma}({}_{\alpha}I_x^{1-\gamma}f(x)) = f(x) \quad (13)$$

The procedure is clarified in the next chapter.

3. Geometry in the Λ fractional space

The theory of the Λ -fractional derivative is explained in the present chapter, discussing the fractional differential geometry of the surface,

$$z = x^{n_1} y^{n_2}, \quad 0 < x < 1, \quad 0 < y < 1 \quad (14)$$

in the initial space x,y based upon the Λ - fractional derivative. The fractional Λ -space (X, Y, Z) is defined by,

$$X = \frac{x^{2-\gamma}}{\Gamma(3-\gamma)} \quad (15)$$

$$Y = \frac{y^{2-\gamma}}{\Gamma(3-\gamma)} \quad (16)$$

$$Z = {}_b^{1-\gamma} I_x^{1-\gamma} z(x, y) = \frac{1}{(\Gamma(1-\gamma))^2} \int_b^y \left(\int_a^x \frac{z(s, t)}{(x-s)^\gamma} ds \right) \frac{dt}{(y-t)^\gamma}, \quad (17)$$

with $a = b = 0$, equation (17) yields,

$$Z(X, Y) = AX^{\left(\frac{1+n_1-\gamma}{2-\gamma}\right)} Y^{\left(\frac{1+n_2-\gamma}{2-\gamma}\right)}, \quad (18)$$

with

$$A = \left[\frac{\Gamma(1+n_1)\Gamma(1+n_2)}{\Gamma(2+n_1-\gamma)\Gamma(2+n_2-\gamma)} \right] [\Gamma(3-\gamma)]^{\left(\frac{2+n_1+n_2-2\gamma}{2-\gamma}\right)} \quad (19)$$

Proceeding to the derivation of the surface $Z(X, Y)$ in the Λ -space, the derivatives,

$$\frac{dZ}{dX} = A \cdot \left(\frac{1+n_1-\gamma}{2-\gamma} \right) \cdot X^{\frac{n_1-1}{2-\gamma}} \cdot Y^{\frac{1+n_2-\gamma}{2-\gamma}} \quad (20)$$

$$\frac{dZ}{dY} = A \cdot \left(\frac{1+n_2-\gamma}{2-\gamma} \right) \cdot X^{\frac{1+n_1-\gamma}{2-\gamma}} \cdot Y^{\frac{n_2-1}{2-\gamma}} \quad (21)$$

Transferring the expressions (20)-(21) into the initial space, not as derivatives but as functions, those functions may be expressed with variables of the initial space by,

$$\frac{dZ}{dX} = \left[\frac{A \cdot \left(\frac{1+n_1-\gamma}{2-\gamma}\right)}{[\Gamma(3-\gamma)]^{\left(\frac{n_1+n_2-\gamma}{2-\gamma}\right)}} \right] \cdot x^{n_1-1} \cdot y^{1+n_2-\gamma} = B_1 \cdot x^{n_1-1} \cdot y^{1+n_2-\gamma} \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{dZ}{dY} = \left[\frac{A \cdot \left(\frac{1+n_2-\gamma}{2-\gamma}\right)}{[\Gamma(3-\gamma)]^{\left(\frac{n_1+n_2-\gamma}{2-\gamma}\right)}} \right] \cdot x^{1+n_1-1} \cdot y^{n_2-1} = B_2 \cdot x^{1+n_1-1} \cdot y^{n_2-1} \quad (23)$$

The functions equations (22)-(23) are transferred from the dual fractional Λ -space to the initial space through the transformations,

$$\begin{aligned} {}_0^{RL}D_y^{1-\gamma}({}_0^{RL}D_x^{1-\gamma}(\frac{dZ}{dX})) &= B_1 \cdot {}_0^{RL}D_y^{1-\gamma}(y^{1+n_2-\gamma}) \cdot {}_0^{RL}D_x^{1-\gamma}(x^{n_1-1}) \\ &= [B_1 \cdot \frac{(\Gamma(n_1) \cdot \Gamma(2+n_2-\gamma))}{\Gamma(1+n_2) \cdot \Gamma(n_1+\gamma-1)}] \cdot x^{n_1+\gamma-1} \cdot y^{n_2} = C_1 \cdot x^{n_1+\gamma-1} \cdot y^{n_2} \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

$$\begin{aligned} {}_0^{RL}D_y^{1-\gamma}({}_0^{RL}D_x^{1-\gamma}(\frac{dZ}{dY})) &= B_2 \cdot {}_0^{RL}D_y^{1-\gamma}(y^{n_2-1}) \cdot {}_0^{RL}D_x^{1-\gamma}(x^{1+n_1-\gamma}) \\ &= [B_2 \frac{\Gamma(n_2)\Gamma(2+n_1-\gamma)}{\Gamma(1+n_1)\Gamma(n_2+\gamma-1)}]x^{n_1}y^{n_2+\gamma-1} = C_2y^{n_2+\gamma-1}x^{n_1}, \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

It is evident that the tangent space of $Z(X, Y)$ at the point (X_0, Y_0) in the dual Λ -fractional space is defined by,

$$Z_t(X, Y) = Z(X_0, Y_0) + \frac{dZ}{dX}|_{(X_0, Y_0)} \cdot (X - X_0) + \frac{dZ}{dY}|_{(X_0, Y_0)}(Y - Y_0) \quad (26)$$

Transferring the tangent function into the initial space, the surface $z_t(x, y)$ corresponding to the tangent space $Z_t(X, Y)$ in the Λ -space is defined by:

$$\begin{aligned} z_t(x, y) &= z(x_0, y_0) + {}_0^{RL}D_y^{1-\gamma}({}_0^{RL}D_x^{1-\gamma}(\frac{dZ}{dX}))|_{(x_0, y_0)} \cdot (\frac{x^{2-\gamma}}{\Gamma(3-\gamma)} - X_0) \\ &\quad + {}_0^{RL}D_y^{1-\gamma}({}_0^{RL}D_x^{1-\gamma}(\frac{dZ}{dY}))|_{(x_0, y_0)} \cdot (\frac{y^{2-\gamma}}{\Gamma(3-\gamma)} - Y_0) \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Applying the aforementioned theory to the surface $z(x, y) = x^2 \cdot y$ in the initial space ($n_1 = 2, n_2 = 1$), see Fig. 1

Figure 1. The surface $z(x, y) = x^2y$ in the initial space.

Considering the equations (18),(20),(21), the surface $Z(X, Y)$ with $\gamma = 0.6$, its tangent plane at the point $(X_0, Y_0) = (0.6, 0.6)$ is shown in Fig. 2.

Recalling equation (11), the point $(X_0, Y_0) = (0.6, 0.6)$ of the dual Λ -space corresponds to $(x_0, y_0) = (0.81, 0.81)$ of the initial space. Hence, the surface $z(x, y)$ with the tangent surface corresponding to tangent plane is shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 2. The corresponding surface in the Λ -space with $\gamma=0.6$ and its tangent plane at the point $(X_0, Y_0) = (0.6, 0.6)$.

Figure 3. The surface $z(x, y)$ with its tangent surface in the initial space

4. The Maxwell's Equations

The conventional Maxwell's electromagnetic equations of integer order are expressed considering the quantities:

\mathbf{H} =magnetic field

\mathbf{D} =dielectric displacement

\mathbf{E} =Electric field

\mathbf{J} =density of electric current

\mathbf{B} =magnetic induction

ρ = charge density.

Those functions depend on space variables x, y, z and the time t . The conventional Maxwell's equations are, Ampere's law

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \mathbf{J} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \quad (28)$$

Faraday's law,

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{D}}{\partial t}. \quad (29)$$

The continuity equation,

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} = \rho \quad (30)$$

And the non-existence of monopole magnetic

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \quad (31)$$

Also, the wave equations

$$v^2 \nabla^2 \mathbf{B} - \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{B}}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (32)$$

$$v^2 \nabla^2 \mathbf{E} - \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{E}}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (33)$$

where v is the wave velocity.

Let us point out that the aforementioned Maxwell's equations are valid in the Λ -space, where differential exists and also fractional differential geometry is developed. Then the equations are transferred from the fractional Λ -space to the initial one, applying the law,

$$f(x, y, z, t) = {}_0^{RL} D_z^{1-\gamma} ({}_0^{RL} D_y^{1-\gamma} ({}_0^{RL} D_x^{1-\gamma} ({}_0^{RL} D_t^{1-\gamma} (F(x, y, z, t)))))) \quad (34)$$

Therefore all the quantities concerning Maxwell's equations may be transferred from the Λ -fractional space to the initial one. The application that follows explains the various stages of the proposed method.

5. Application

Consider in the Λ - fractional space,

$$\mathbf{E} = E_m \sin(\omega T - \beta X) \mathbf{k} \quad (35)$$

in free space. Find D, B, H in the original space. Sketch E and H in the original space with $\omega = \beta = 1$ and $T = 0.2$.

The Maxwell equation $\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial T}$ yields in the Λ -fractional space

$$\mathbf{B} = \frac{\beta E_m}{\omega} \sin(\omega T - \beta X) \mathbf{k} \quad (36)$$

with neglected constant of integration. Then,

$$\mathbf{H} = -\frac{\beta H_m}{\omega} \sin(\omega T - \beta X) \mathbf{j} \quad (37)$$

Considering $\beta = \omega = 1$ we get:

$$E(T, X) = E_m \cdot \sin(T - X) \quad (38)$$

$$H(T, X) = -H_m \cdot \sin(T - X)$$

with $H_m = \frac{E_m}{\mu_0}$.

Those fields valid in the Λ -fractional space, expressed in the variables of the initial space are,

$$E(t, x) = E_m \cdot \sin \left(\frac{t^{2-\gamma_2}}{\Gamma(3-\gamma_2)} - \frac{x^{2-\gamma_1}}{\Gamma(3-\gamma_1)} \right) \quad (39)$$

$$H(t, x) = -H_m \cdot \sin \left(\frac{t^{2-\gamma_1}}{\Gamma(3-\gamma_2)} - \frac{x^{2-\gamma_1}}{\Gamma(3-\gamma_1)} \right) \quad (40)$$

Transferring the various quantities into the initial space (x, y, z, t) with the fractional order of space γ_1 and time γ_2 the fields $E(t, x)$ and $H(t, x)$ in the initial space may be computed through the relations,

$$E(t, x) = {}_0^{RL}D_t^{1-\gamma_2} ({}_0^{RL}D_x^{1-\gamma_1}(E(t, x))) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\gamma_2) \cdot \Gamma(\gamma_1)} \cdot \frac{d}{dt} \int_0^t \frac{1}{(t-\tau)^{1-\gamma_2}} \left(\frac{d}{dx} \int_0^x \frac{E(\tau, s)}{(x-s)^{1-\gamma_1}} ds \right) d\tau \quad (41)$$

$$H(t, x) = {}_0^{RL}D_t^{1-\gamma_2} ({}_0^{RL}D_x^{1-\gamma_1}(H(t, x))) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\gamma_2)\Gamma(\gamma_1)} \cdot \frac{d}{dt} \int_0^t \frac{1}{(t-\tau)^{1-\gamma_2}} \left(\frac{d}{dx} \int_0^x \frac{H(\tau, s)}{(x-s)^{1-\gamma_1}} ds \right) d\tau \quad (42)$$

For the present application the fields $E(T, X)$ and $H(T, X)$ with,

$$E(T, X) = E_m \sin(T - X) \quad (43)$$

$$H(T, X) = -H_m \sin(T - X) \quad (44)$$

have been considered with $E_m = H_m = 2$.

For $T = 0.2$, the diagram of $E(X)$ is shown in Fig. 4:

Figure 4. The electric field $E(X)$ in the Λ -fractional space for time $T = 0.2$

Further, for fractional time order $\gamma_2 = 0.4$, time $T = 0.2$ corresponds to, see equation (11), to $t = 0.45725$. Taking into consideration, equations (41),(42) the electric fields in the original space have been computed and are shown in Fig. 5 for fractional space order $\gamma_1 = 0.3, 0.5, 0.7$ and 0.9 . The same comment on the increase of width and frequency on space distribution of the Electric field $E(x, t)$ is valid in the present case.

Figure 5. The electric field $E(X)$ in the initial space for time $t = 0.457$ and $\gamma_2 = 0.4$ for various γ_1 .

It is evident that the width of the wave of the electric field is increased with decreasing fractional space order. Further, decreasing the fractional space order the width and the frequency with respect to space of the electric field distribution is increased. Increasing time fractional order $\gamma_2 = 0.6$, the real time t corresponding to $T = 0.2$ in the Λ - fractional space is $t = 0.36983$. The diagrams of the electric field $E(x)$ in the true initial space for various space fractional orders γ_1 have been computed and are shown in Fig. 6,

Figure 6. The electric field $E(X)$ in the initial space for time $t = 0.37$ and $\gamma_2 = 0.6$ for various γ_1 .

The same comment on the increase of width and frequency on space distribution of the Electric field $E(x, t)$ in the initial space is valid in the present case. Increasing time fractional order $\gamma_2 = 0.8$, the real time t corresponding to $T = 0.2$ in the Λ - fractional space is $t = 0.28354$. The diagrams of the electric field $E(x)$ in the true initial space for various space fractional orders γ_1 have been computed and are shown in Fig. 7,

Figure 7. The electric field $E(X)$ in the initial space for time $t = 0.28$ and $\gamma_2 = 0.8$ for various γ_1 .

Figure 8. The Magnetic field $H(T)$ in the Λ -fractional space for $T=0.2$.

As it is shown in Figures 5,6,7, it is evident that increasing the time fractional order, the width of the electric field $E(x,t)$ is increased. Proceeding to the corresponding magnetic field in the Λ -fractional space for $T = 0.2$ we get the diagram, see Fig. 8

Figure 9. The magnetic field $H(X)$ in the initial space for time $t = 0.457$ and $\gamma_2 = 0.4$ for various γ_1

Transferring the magnetic field into the initial space for various time fractional orders γ_2 and space fractional orders γ_1 the magnetic field distribution has been computed. For the time fractional order $\gamma_2 = 0.4$, the time $T = 0.2$, in the Λ - fractional space corresponds to $t = 0.45725$ in the initial space. It is shown in Fig. 9 the distribution of the magnetic field $H(t)$ for various space fractional orders γ_1 .

Figure 10. The magnetic field $H(X)$ in the initial space for time $t = 0.37$ and $\gamma_2 = 0.6$ for various γ_1 .

Transferring the magnetic field into the initial space for $\gamma_2 = 0.6$, the time $T = 0.2$, in the Λ - fractional space, corresponds to $t = 0.37$ in the initial space. It is shown in Fig. 10 shows the distribution of the magnetic field $H(t)$ in the initial space for various space fractional orders γ_1 .

Figure 11. The magnetic field $H(X)$ in the initial space for time $t = 0.29$ and $\gamma_2 = 0.8$ for various γ_1

Transferring the magnetic field into the initial space for $\gamma_2 = 0.8$, the time $T = 0.2$, in the Λ -fractional space, corresponds to $t = 0.28354$ in the initial space. It is shown in Fig. 11 the distribution of the magnetic field $H(t)$ in the initial space for various space fractional orders γ_1 .

It is concluded, as a general comment, that the width of the electric and magnetic fields are increased with increasing fractional time orders, while they are decreased with fractional space orders.

6. Conclusion

The non-local Maxwell's electromagnetic theory has been presented with the help of Λ -fractional Analysis. Since Λ -fractional Analysis deals with derivatives conforming with the prerequisites of Differential Topology for generating Differential Geometry, in the introduced Λ -fractional space, the various non-local fractional Maxwell's equations are formulated with both fractional time and fractional space. The example indicates that the widths of the electric and magnetic fields are increased with increasing fractional time and decreasing fractional space orders.

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